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Academic Stress and Coping Mechanisms of Grade 6 Learners in Calamba City: Basis for an Action Plan

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Abstract

This study examines the level of academic stress and coping mechanisms among Grade 6 students, focusing on various stressors such as peer-related issues, self-inflicted pressures, career-related concerns, and time management challenges. Using a survey method, the study analyzes the responses of students on their perceived academic stress in relation to these factors. The results indicate that students experience significant stress primarily from their perceived academic performance compared to peers and the difficulty in balancing academic and social activities. The highest levels of stress were linked to concerns about academic results, with students feeling worried that their performance was not on par with their classmates. Additionally, students expressed difficulties in managing their time effectively, often feeling overwhelmed by academic and social obligations. In terms of coping strategies, the study reveals that students rely more on passive methods such as watching uplifting movies, spending time with pets, and creating a calming environment, with less emphasis on active strategies like physical activity or seeking help from teachers. The findings suggest that while students employ coping mechanisms to alleviate stress, these strategies are not sufficient to address the root causes. This research highlights the need for targeted interventions to support students in managing academic stress and developing more effective coping mechanisms. Schools are encouraged to provide guidance on time management, stress reduction techniques, and emotional well-being to help students navigate academic challenges more effectively.

Keywords: *user-centered, word game-based, approach in teaching, pupils' learning achievement*

Introduction

Academic stress can significantly impact students' health and well-being, often impeding their academic progress due to pressures related to academics, social interactions, finances, and peer competition, ultimately leading to underperformance (Yousif et al., 2022). Wilks (2018) described academic stress as a combination of scholastic demands that surpass an individual's adaptive capacity. Ramli et al. (2018) further identified academic stress as a prevalent issue among medical students during training phases, attributed to increasing academic requirements, high workloads, peer rivalry, examinations, and time management challenges. According to recent reports, general stress levels have been rising steadily since 2014, with younger generations particularly susceptible (American Psychological Association, 2018; Statista, 2018). Consequently, understanding the nature and sources of stress among students is essential, as academic demands are increasingly recognized as a leading stressor (Reddy et al., 2018).

In terms of health implications, chronic stress has been linked to various physical and mental health issues, including hypertension, anxiety, and depression, as noted by Harvard Health (2024). Additionally, preliminary studies suggest that stress-related lifestyle changes, such as reduced physical activity, may contribute to obesity. Studies show that academic stress is also becoming a growing concern among primary school children, as they face heightened academic expectations, the need to perform well on assessments, and parental expectations (Vanaelst et al., 2022; Treceñe et al., 2021). The inability to manage these pressures may lead to feelings of hopelessness, hinder the development of essential skills, and negatively impact attitudes toward learning and participation in broader life activities (Pistonia, 2022; Education et al., 2018).

Research has also emphasized the complexity of academic stress among sixth graders as they transition to middle school, taking on more subjects and adapting to new teachers and environments (Deng et al., 2022; Egan et al., 2023). Filade (2019) identified peer pressure as an additional stressor, highlighting its role in driving students to achieve academically to gain social acceptance. High-stakes testing and standardized exams further add to the pressure, as performance on these assessments can significantly influence students' educational pathways.

The past decade has seen a marked rise in academic pressure among students due to increased assignments, exams, and extracurricular obligations. Jain and Singhai (2018) found that students are often pressured by parents and teachers to excel, resulting in stress and, at times, burnout. Parents also encourage extracurricular involvement, expecting students to develop into well-rounded individuals, though this can contribute to confusion and difficulty in career planning (Moneva et al., 2020). Peer pressure further compounds stress, affecting students' confidence and leading to both positive and negative personality changes (Peer Pressure Essay for Students and Children, 2019). While moderate stress may have beneficial effects on memory and problem-solving (Scott, 2024), excessive stress can lead to anxiety, depression, and compromised academic performance (Mckean et al., 2020).

To address these challenges, the Department of Education in the Philippines has implemented initiatives such as Sulong Edukalidad and the MATATAG agenda, emphasizing quality education, improved learning facilities, and teacher development. These initiatives aim to support students' academic growth while promoting holistic well-being (Academ-e Multi Media Solutions Inc., 2024).

Additionally, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) underscore the importance of good health, quality education, and inclusive learning opportunities, which are critical for student success and well-being (Martin, 2023; Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2023).

This study seeks to address a noticeable gap in research by examining the unique stressors faced by elementary students, particularly Grade 6 learners within Cluster 1 in Calamba City. Observations indicate that academic stress may be linked to decreased test scores in key subjects, such as English, Mathematics, and Science (Amon et al., 2023). This study aims to provide insights into the challenges these young students face, contributing to the development of targeted strategies to support their coping abilities and academic success in the context of the evolving educational landscape.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the level of academic stress and the coping mechanisms of Grade 6 learners in Calamba City. Specifically, it seeks to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of academic stress experienced by the respondents in relation to:
 - 1.1. Group-related characteristics;
 - 1.2. Peer-related characteristics;
 - 1.3. Self-inflicted issues;
 - 1.4. Career-related issues; and
 - 1.5. Time management practices?
2. What coping mechanisms are utilized by the respondents?
3. Based on the findings, what compendium of coping strategies may be proposed to support the respondents?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design with a quantitative approach, primarily using a survey questionnaire. According to Bhandari (2020), quantitative research involves gathering and analyzing numerical data to find patterns, predict outcomes, and generalize results to a broader population. This design was suitable for assessing academic stress levels and coping mechanisms among Grade 6 students, as it allowed a detailed examination of these factors across a large sample.

Respondents

The study surveyed 281 Grade 6 students from five schools in Calamba City, Laguna: Halang Elementary School, Bucal Elementary School, E. Baretto Sr. Elementary School, La Mesa Elementary School, and Tiyani Elementary School, all part of Cluster 1 in the district. These students were selected from a larger population of 1,035 Grade 6 learners during the 2023-2024 school year. Grade 6 students were chosen due to their transitional stage from primary to secondary school, a time often marked by increased academic demands and stress. Their age makes them capable of self-reflection and expression, providing valuable insight into their stress and coping strategies.

A purposive sampling method was used, allowing the researcher to select students who fit specific study criteria. This approach ensured the sample's relevance to the research objectives, targeting students likely to experience academic stress at this transitional educational stage. Using the Raosoft Calculator, the sample size was calculated with a 95% confidence level to ensure that the results were representative and statistically sound.

Instrument

The study used a survey questionnaire adapted from Nallapati et al. (2020), divided into two main sections. Part 1 measured academic stress levels across five categories: group-related characteristics, peer-related characteristics, self-inflicted issues, career-related issues, and time management practices. Part 2 assessed the coping mechanisms students used to manage stress. Both sections used a four-point Likert scale, offering structured responses to capture the intensity of academic stress and the frequency of coping methods.

Procedure

The data collection process involved several steps:

Permissions: Approval was obtained from university and school officials, ensuring the study followed institutional guidelines. A memorandum informed participants about the study.

Survey Administration: In face-to-face sessions, students were briefed on the study's purpose, risks, and benefits. Informed consent forms were provided and signed by participants or their guardians.

Data Collection and Confidentiality: The survey was conducted based on students' available time to minimize disruption. Responses were collected anonymously and used solely for research.

Data Processing: Collected responses were tallied and forwarded to a statistician for analysis.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using the mean, standard deviation, and percentage. The mean measured the average academic stress and coping levels, while the standard deviation assessed the variability within responses. Percentages indicated the proportion of students facing various stress levels or using specific coping mechanisms, providing a clear view of prevalent issues among respondents.

This methodical approach provided a comprehensive analysis of academic stress and coping strategies among Grade 6 students, offering insights that could support strategies for stress management at this educational stage.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Level of Academic Stress in terms of Group-related Characteristics*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I often face problems as to how to share work with my classmates when some exercises or reports require group work	2.95	A
2. When group work is required to complete an exercise or report, I worry that I will not be able to find a suitable group member	2.40	A
3. When I give a speech or presentation, I worry that my classmates will laugh at my inability to perform well	3.38	CA
4. I feel nervous when I need to make a speech or give a presentation	3.54	CA
Overall Mean	3.07	A

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Completely Agree (CA); 2.51 – 3.25 Agree (A); 1.76 – 2.50 Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.75 Completely Disagree (CD)

The data in Table 1.1 illustrates that Grade 6 learners experience academic stress related to group activities, reflected by an overall mean score of 3.07, which indicates general agreement on stress in this area. The highest stress levels were noted when students needed to give speeches or presentations, with mean scores of 3.54 and 3.38, showing that students were particularly nervous about public speaking and concerned about negative peer reactions. This aligns with findings by Grieve et al. (2021), who identified fear of public speaking as a common manifestation of Social Anxiety Disorder (SAD), which can hinder students' public speaking abilities and social engagement in class.

Additionally, students reported difficulties in managing group work, with mean scores of 2.95 and 2.40 on issues related to task sharing and finding suitable group partners. These results suggest that while students are somewhat comfortable with group dynamics, specific challenges still create stress. Concerns about choosing compatible group members and equitable task sharing are notable stress points, reflecting the importance of social compatibility and cooperative skills in academic settings.

The implications of these findings are twofold. First, students may experience elevated academic stress when required to perform individually in front of peers, likely due to fears of social judgment or a lack of confidence in public speaking skills. This type of stress can be particularly impactful during presentations or speeches, where perceived peer judgment may amplify their anxiety. Second, the stress associated with group-related tasks indicates that social dynamics within groups can either alleviate or exacerbate academic stress, depending on how comfortable students feel collaborating and depending on peers. These findings suggest that developing both individual presentation skills and collaborative strategies can help alleviate stress related to group work.

Table 2. *Level of Academic Stress in terms of Peer-related Characteristics*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. When I want to study on my own, I am often affected by my classmates' chatting	2.91	A
2. I feel that my classmates are very noisy during class and this influences my class situations	2.76	A
3. I am concerned about the academic competition with my peer group	2.28	A
4. I am very worried that my academic results are not as good as those of my classmates	3.10	A
5. I feel left out when my peer group discusses learnt concepts in their native languages	2.90	A
Overall Mean	2.79	A

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Completely Agree (CA); 2.51 – 3.25 Agree (A); 1.76 – 2.50 Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.75 Completely Disagree (CD)

The data in Table 2, with an overall mean of 2.79, indicates that Grade 6 learners generally experience academic stress in relation to peer dynamics. The highest stress level, reflected by a mean score of 3.10, was associated with students' worries about their academic results not measuring up to those of their classmates. This concern suggests that students experience stress more from comparing their own achievements to those of their peers rather than from any explicit academic competition.

The results highlight that academic stress among Grade 6 learners is shaped by self-comparison with peers, potentially leading to feelings of inadequacy and stress when academic results fall short of peers' achievements. This aligns with findings by Jiang et al. (2022), which indicate that students with lower academic performance may be particularly vulnerable to peer influence, which can intensify feelings of inferiority, anxiety, and academic-related fear. This form of peer-related stress may stem from students' internalized

perceptions of success as judged against their social group, rather than external competition.

Other indicators with notable mean scores, such as distractions from classmates' chatting (2.91) and feelings of exclusion when peers discuss topics in native languages (2.90), reflect additional sources of stress related to classroom social dynamics. These findings suggest that while social connections can be supportive, they can also introduce stress when learners feel academically or socially misaligned with their peers.

Table 3. *Level of Academic Stress in terms of Self-inflicted Issues*

Indicators		Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	I feel that my learning level is not as good as that of my classmates	3.28	A
2.	I feel that I have so many topics to read and that I am out of breath	2.87	A
3.	I feel that I have no interest in some subjects	2.83	A
4.	I feel that after I entered university, my performance was not as good as I had expected	2.54	A
5.	On missing few lectures I feel anxious about falling short of attendance towards the end	2.93	A
Overall Mean		2.89	A

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Completely Agree (CA); 2.51 – 3.25 Agree (A); 1.76 – 2.50 Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.75 Completely Disagree (CD)

The data in Table 3, with an overall mean of 2.89, suggests that Grade 6 learners experience moderate academic stress related to self-inflicted issues. The highest mean score of 3.28 reflects that students commonly feel their learning does not measure up to their classmates. This tendency to self-compare may heighten feelings of inadequacy and stress.

Interestingly, concerns about university performance rank lower, with a mean of 2.54, indicating that these students are more focused on their current academic standing than on future challenges. This aligns with the big-fish-little-pond effect (BFLPE), as noted by Jansen et al. (2022), where students gauge their self-perception against the average performance of their peers. This peer-comparison can intensify immediate stress and anxiety as they measure themselves against those around them, emphasizing short-term academic pressures over long-term goals.

Table 4. *Level of Academic Stress in terms of Career-related Issues*

Indicators		Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	There is lack of counselling on career-related issues in the college campus	2.86	A
2.	Uncertainty about job placement worries me	3.18	A
3.	Thought of peers getting a placement ahead of me bothers me	2.83	A
Overall Mean		2.96	A

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Completely Agree (CA); 2.51 – 3.25 Agree (A); 1.76 – 2.50 Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.75 Completely Disagree (CD)

The data in Table 4, with an overall mean of 2.96, indicates that Grade 6 students experience moderate academic stress related to career concerns. The highest mean score of 3.18 reflects students' uncertainty about job placement, suggesting that concerns about future employment are already significant at this stage.

This stress is not solely tied to current academic pressures but extends to career anxieties, indicating early awareness of job security as an important factor. Interestingly, the lower concern over peers securing placements ahead of them (mean of 2.83) shows that students focus more on their own career uncertainties rather than on competition with others. This self-focused stress suggests an intrinsic pressure to succeed. The findings align with De La Fuente et al. (2020), who observed that career anxiety could drive students to work diligently, perhaps as a way to mitigate fears about future career prospects.

Table 5. *Level of Academic Stress in terms of Time Management Practices*

Indicators		Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	I feel that it is very difficult for me to find a balance between my academic and social activities	3.26	CA
2.	I feel that the time spent on social activities and student associations affect my academic work	2.49	A
3.	I find difficulty in sticking to my study time table during examinations	2.83	A
4.	I regret that I wasted time set apart for studies	3.04	A
Overall Mean		2.79	A

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Completely Agree (CA); 2.51 – 3.25 Agree (A); 1.76 – 2.50 Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.75 Completely Disagree (CD)

The data in Table 5, with an overall mean of 2.79, reflects that Grade 6 students experience moderate academic stress related to time management practices. The highest-scoring indicator, with a mean of 3.26, reveals that students find it particularly challenging to balance academic responsibilities with social activities, indicating that many feel stretched between schoolwork and other engagements. This struggle to maintain equilibrium likely adds substantial stress to their academic experience.

Indicator 2, with the lowest mean score of 2.49, shows that although students recognize that social activities may affect their academic work, they don't perceive it as strongly as the challenge of balancing these activities. This could suggest that while they acknowledge the impact of social activities, the primary stressor is finding a way to juggle multiple demands.

The findings imply that Grade 6 students may lack effective strategies for managing their time, which could hinder their ability to perform well academically while still engaging socially. Additionally, difficulty in adhering to study timetables and regret over lost study time (as indicated by means of 2.83 and 3.04, respectively) suggests that these students might struggle with consistency and self-discipline, further contributing to their academic stress.

These insights support Jacqui (2024), who emphasizes the importance of balance between academics and other life areas in educational settings. While maintaining this balance is crucial, it is a uniquely personal journey that varies with each individual's capacity and circumstances. Although Grade 6 students are not in college, they already experience the strain of balancing multiple responsibilities, highlighting the need for targeted support in time management.

Helping students develop better time management skills and providing strategies for balancing academic and social activities may alleviate some of their stress. By fostering awareness and teaching practical skills, educators can equip students to handle academic demands while also enjoying their social lives, helping them develop habits that will benefit them in the long run.

Table 6. *Coping Mechanisms*

<i>Coping Mechanisms</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1.	Listening to music	2.80	S
2.	Taking short breaks during study sessions	3.13	S
3.	Deep breathing exercises	2.85	S
4.	Going for a walk or bike ride	2.82	S
5.	Talking to a friend or family member about concerns	2.96	S
6.	Drawing or doodling to relax the mind	2.62	S
7.	Writing in a journal to express thoughts and feelings	3.03	S
8.	Doing simple stretching exercises	2.38	S
9.	Playing with pets	3.21	S
10.	Spending time outdoors in nature	2.96	S
11.	Engaging in a favorite hobby or activity	3.02	S
12.	Watching a funny or uplifting movie or TV show	3.27	A
13.	Taking a warm bath or shower	3.07	S
14.	Creating a calming environment	3.14	S
15.	Practicing mindfulness or meditation techniques	2.46	S
16.	Setting realistic goals and prioritizing tasks	2.87	S
17.	Asking for help from teachers or classmates when needed	2.97	S
18.	Rewarding oneself after completing tasks or achieving goals	3.13	S
19.	Using positive self-talk and affirmations	2.83	S
20.	Getting enough sleep and maintaining a healthy lifestyle	2.78	S
Overall Mean		2.89	S

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Always (A); 2.51 – 3.25 Often (O); 1.76 – 2.50 Sometimes (S); 1.00 – 1.75 Never (N)

The data from Table 6 indicate that Grade 6 students use a variety of coping mechanisms to manage academic stress, with an overall mean of 2.89, which falls under the “often” category. Among these, watching a funny or uplifting movie or TV show has the highest mean score of 3.27, interpreted as “always.” This suggests that many students turn to passive entertainment as a consistent means of coping. Other frequently used methods include playing with pets, creating a calming environment, rewarding themselves after completing tasks, and asking for help from teachers or classmates, all of which fall within the “often” range.

The preference for passive coping mechanisms, such as watching movies, playing with pets, or engaging in hobbies, may indicate a tendency among students to seek mental distraction and emotional comfort rather than engaging in more physically active or mindful practices. While some students do engage in activities like deep breathing exercises, spending time outdoors, or practicing mindfulness, these methods have lower mean scores, indicating they are used less consistently.

This preference aligns with Makarova and Gur'eva's (2023) findings, which emphasize that coping mechanisms are essential for navigating stress, with individuals often choosing methods that align with their comfort and accessibility. The students' reliance on accessible, comforting activities like movies and social support from friends or family reflects a need for immediate stress relief and emotional reassurance in their academic environment.

These findings highlight an opportunity for educators and caregivers to introduce students to a broader range of active coping techniques, such as structured mindfulness practices or physical exercises, which could complement their existing methods and potentially enhance their stress resilience. By expanding the range of coping skills and encouraging the adoption of both active and passive techniques, students may be better equipped to manage stress in both academic and future life settings.

Conclusions

This study highlights the various sources of academic stress and coping mechanisms employed by Grade 6 students. The results show that students experience significant stress from peer-related issues, self-inflicted pressures, career uncertainties, and time management

challenges. Most notably, students expressed concerns about their academic performance relative to peers, which was a major source of stress. Additionally, the struggle to balance academic work with social activities further intensified their stress levels. Despite these pressures, students tend to rely on passive coping strategies such as watching uplifting movies or spending time with pets. While these methods offer temporary relief, they do not address the root causes of stress. The study also emphasizes the importance of understanding how students' self-perceptions contribute to academic stress, particularly as they internalize academic expectations. These findings suggest that Grade 6 students are already grappling with pressures typically faced in higher education, indicating the need for more effective support systems. Ultimately, addressing both the internal and external factors contributing to stress, and promoting proactive coping strategies, can help students navigate their academic journey more effectively and reduce overall stress levels.

To alleviate academic stress and improve overall well-being, it is recommended that educational institutions provide more targeted support in managing stress. Implementing programs that teach effective time management, stress reduction techniques, and emotional regulation skills will help students better handle academic pressures. Schools should also encourage the development of active coping strategies, such as physical activity, mindfulness, and seeking help from teachers or peers, to complement passive methods like relaxation or entertainment. Additionally, educators and counselors should offer more guidance regarding career prospects, helping students understand that academic stress is a natural part of personal and academic growth, and that future success is not solely defined by immediate academic performance. Peer support systems and mentorship programs could also be beneficial in reducing feelings of inadequacy. Furthermore, fostering an environment where students can express their concerns openly and access resources to manage their stress will promote better mental health and academic success. By implementing these measures, schools can provide a balanced and supportive environment, helping students build resilience and manage stress more effectively.

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